

An Analysis of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) to Promote Financial Inclusion in India

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Abstract

Despite over 78 years of independence and several Financial-Economic reforms, a significant segment of our populace remains deprived from formal banking and financial services. The impoverished are consequently denied opportunities to invest, save money, or get credit. The Reserve Bank of India and the Government of India have attempted multiple times to bring financial inclusion to the financially excluded elements of society. Additionally, our government is attempting to address this issue through Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), a new programme. India's National Mission for Financial Inclusion effort is called PMJDY. The PMJDY makes sure that the weaker and poorer segments of society can access banking and financial services at a fair price. The Government of India launched PMJDY on August 28, 2014. This scheme was begun more than nine years ago. It is necessary to assess PMJDY. Therefore, an attempt has been made to examine the status of financial inclusion in India before and after PMJDY's launching, as well as PMJDY's contribution to greater financial inclusion. This research paper is based on secondary data from various research Paper, reports, Government official website etc. This research paper concludes with some suggestions for effective implementation of PMJDY scheme.

Keywords

Financial Inclusion, PMJDY, savings, formal banking facility, and valunerable sections etc.

Introduction

Each and every economic activity depends heavily on finance. Each and every social class needs money as well. Since the outset, the financial needs of only the upper and middle classes of society have been met. Financing is extremely difficult for the underprivileged and vulnerable members of society to get. On the other hand, these groups must be able to access money in order to find work, end poverty, and achieve social and economic empowerment. Therefore, there is a pressing need to connect financial inclusion with the underprivileged and disadvantaged segments of society. Making financial services available to people in society who are impoverished and have low incomes is the aim of financial inclusion, also known as inclusive finance.

Financial inclusion promotes equality among the populace and gives disadvantaged groups more influence. The potential for impoverished people to save money, invest, and obtain loans is made possible by financial inclusion. Access to financial services also helps the impoverished be better prepared for events such as illness, death of a family member, and job loss. It also helps them guard against sudden drops in income. Furthermore, financial inclusion makes it possible for the government to send funds from social security, subsidies, and MNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme) wages directly into the bank accounts of beneficiaries. Government of India placed great emphasis on inclusive growth in all welfare measures, with the 12th Plan (2012–17) primarily aimed at achieving sustainable inclusive growth, in light of the significance of financial inclusion.

Strong attempts have been made in India to integrate the economically marginalised members of society. In order to promote financial inclusion, the government established a commission in 2004 and appointed Shri H.R. Khan as its head. There were big plans once the Rangarajan Committee Report was published in 2008. The Nationalisation of Banks, the Lead Bank Scheme, the Relaxation of KYC Standards, the Business Correspondents and Facilitators Model, the SHG Bank Linkage Programme, the Introduction of General Credit Cards, Kisan Credit Cards, Direct Benefit Transfer, the Consolidation of Regional Rural Banks, the Performance Appraisal of Bank Staff, and the Roadmap for Banking Services in Unbanked Villages were the main initiatives undertaken by the Government of India and the RBI.

The Indian government started the 'Swabhimaan' campaign in 2011. This effort aimed to give banking services to more than 74,000 villages with a minimum of 2000 residents. Despite these initiatives, there are still notable regional disparities both within and between urban and rural sections of the country. According to the Census of 2011, only 54.4% of rural households and 58.7% of Indian families as a whole had access to formal

banking services. Furthermore, the statistics revealed that 73% of farm households lack a formal credit facility, and just 24.4 million farmer households or 27.3% of the total 89.3 million households had access to institutional credit.

As India's economy grows rapidly, it is important to ensure that all sectors of society share in this progress and that regional inequalities do not stand in the way of this growth. Therefore, there is a great need to provide financial services to all households that are not covered by formal financial services. To meet this need, the Government of India announced on his August 28, 2014 initiative called Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Account (PMJDY) to provide financial services to the rural marginalized and marginalized people. We have started a new program. It has been more than nine years since this program began. Therefore, the PMJDY scheme needs to be evaluated.

Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana(PMJDY)

Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) started on 28 August 2014. The main objective of this scheme is to ensure universal access to banking facilities with at least one basic bank account for every household. The scheme is based on 'Sab kasath sab kavikas'.i.e. inclusive growth through 'Mera Khata Bhagya Vidhata'. Under the scheme, account holders will be provided zero-balance bank account with RuPay debit card. In addition an accidental insurance cover of Rs 1 lakh. They will be given life insurance cover of Rs 30,000. Six months of opening of the bank account, holders can avail Rs 5,000 overdraft facility.

Benefits of PMJDY Schemes

1. Interest on the deposited money.
2. Accidental insurance coverage of Rs. 2 lakhs
3. No minimal balance is required.
4. If the qualifying requirements are met, the policy provides a Rs. 30,000/- life insurance pay-out upon the beneficiary's death.
5. Easy Money Transfers Throughout India
6. The government would make direct benefit transfers to recipients of government schemes in PMJDY accounts.
7. After six months of satisfactory operation, an overdraft facility will be permitted.
8. Insurance and pension plans are available.
9. Any successful financial or nonfinancial customer-induced transaction at any bank branch, Bank Mitra, ATM, POS, or other intra-bank or inter-bank channel that occurs within 90 days of the accident death, including the accident date, will be considered eligible for the benefit of personal accidental insurance claims under the PMJDY Scheme. Only one account per household, ideally the lady of the house, is eligible for a Rs. 10,000 overdraft.

Financial Inclusion

Financial inclusion is the process of ensuring access to appropriate financial products and services needed by vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and Low income groups at an affordable cost in a fair and transparent manner by banking and financial institutions.

The Rangarajan Committee Defined "Financial Inclusion as the process of ensuring access to financial services and timely and adequate credit where needed by vulnerable groups such as weaker section and low income groups at an affordable cost"

RBI defines Financial Inclusion as "A process of ensuring access to appropriate financial products and services needed by all sections of the society in general and vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and low income groups in particular, at an affordable cost in a fair and transparent manner by regulated mainstream institutional players"

Objective of study

The primary goal of this study is to assess the contribution of PMJDY in promotion of financial inclusion in India. Apart from this, the study has the following objectives.

1. To know about PMJDY Scheme: A revolutionary program for financial Inclusion.
2. To evaluate the importance of PMJDY towards financial inclusion in India.
3. To analyze the status of financial inclusion before and after launching of PMJDY in India.
4. To provide some suggestions for effective implementation of PMJDY scheme.

Review of Literature

Numerous academic studies have been published about financial inclusion. These included studies from India as well as other countries. The national mission of financial inclusion known as 'Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY)' has not received much research. Below is a brief summary of the different studies on the PMJDY Scheme that are currently accessible. **Kalaivani and Mani (2025)** provide a comprehensive synthesis of financial inclusion initiatives in India, placing PMJDY at the center. They examine institutional frameworks, digital readiness, and financial literacy as critical pillars for inclusive banking. **Raghuwanshi (2025)** traces the policy evolution of financial inclusion from 2014 to 2025, highlighting PMJDY alongside other flagship programs (JAM trinity, DBT, etc.) and its role in shaping India's inclusive finance architecture. **Thakar and Dave (2025)** conduct a performance analysis (2015–2025), using indicators like the number of accounts, deposits, and RuPay cards. Their findings show that PMJDY has significantly

expanded banking outreach, especially among women and rural populations. **Kaur, Singh, & Mishra (2025)** propose a PMJDY Financial Inclusion Index (PIFI), combining per capita savings accounts, deposits, and RuPay cards. Their regression analyses show a significant positive effect of PMJDY-driven inclusion on state GDP, suggesting broader macroeconomic benefits. **Maity & Majumder (2025)** present a state-wise comparative study of financial inclusion under PMJDY, constructing an index based on banking penetration, disbursement, and services. Their results show that many states still lag, illustrating regional disparities in PMJDY effectiveness. **Bagar & Sijeriya (2024)** study PMJDY adoption in Meerut (UP), examining differences in account holding by gender and caste. Their work reveals that although many accounts are opened, social disparities in access and usage persist. **Divya U, Jogish, Madhumita Mankar, Meti & Manjunatha (2024)** Using primary data and structural equation modeling (SEM), this study finds that PMJDY has a very strong impact (76%) on financial empowerment among rural beneficiaries. However, it also points out under-utilization of facilities: overdraft facility and fund transfer are not widely used due to poor technical infrastructure. **Kurussiveettil & Kanniammal (2024)** This study highlights that among Scheduled Tribe (ST) populations in Kerala, literacy plays a crucial role in financial inclusion via PMJDY. A survey (n = 348) showed that lower literacy severely limits both awareness of the scheme and meaningful usage. The authors argue that without improving financial literacy, PMJDY's goals of "inclusion" risk being superficial. **Dutta Tulika and Ashish Das (2017)** have analysed the data of PMJDY. In this report it has been attempted to summarize and interpret the PMJDY data that the Government of India disseminates. This study's primary goals were to determine the strategies used by various banks and learn what the public thought of those strategies as part of a financial inclusion initiative. The survey revealed that even while banks are adhering to RBI guidelines, there is still more work to be done to advance financial inclusion. According to the report, three parties the RBI, all banks, and the general public must exert effort for financial inclusion to progress. **Chaudhary Alka (2017)** has examined the role and implications of PMJDY in financial inclusion and growth of India. The study came to the conclusion that the PMJDY plan has attracted a significant portion of India's population by offering banking services and financial products at competitive prices. The study recommended implementing a number of initiatives for financial inclusion, including the use of cutting-edge technologies, putting up bank branches in remote regions, providing credit to everyone, entire life insurance coverage, etc.

Methodology

This study is based on certain facts and secondary data. Data required for study are mainly collected through various government web sources, govt. publications and annual report of RBI, different books, journals, newspapers and relevant websites.

Analysis

**Table No. 1: Progress Report of PMJDY
(As on 31 Jan 2015, All figures in CR.)**

Bank	Rural/Semi urban branches	Urban Branches	Total Account	Total deposited Amount(In lacs)	Issued Rupey Debit card
Public bank	53300249	45147276	98447525	817463.04	91232024
RRBs	18489448	3297833	21787281	159948.08	14967614
Private Bank	3226397	2012086	5238483	72551.50	4593161
Total	75016094	50457195	125473289	1049962.62	110792799

Source: Website of PMJDY: www.pmjdy.gov.in

Table No.1 reveals that during six months of the scheme's introduction, from 28/08/2014 to 31/01/2015, more than 12.5 crore accounts were opened with a deposit amount of Rs.10,499.62 crore. More than 7.5 crore (59.78%) of these accounts were opened in rural areas, while more than 5 crore (40.21%) were opened in urban areas. The table also reveals that Public Sector banks opened more than 9.8 crore (78%) accounts, Rural Regional Banks (RRB's) opened more than 2.17 crore (17%) accounts, and Private banks established only 4% accounts. Beneficiaries received around 11.07 crore Rupay debit

cards.

Table No. 2: Progress Report of PMJDY
(As on 15/10/2025, All figures in CR.)

Bank	Rural/Semi urban branches	Urban Branches	No. Of Rural-Urban Female Beneficiaries	Total Account	Total deposited Amount	Issued Rupey Debit card
Public Sector Bank	34.18	9.82	24.28	44.01	214733.16	33.75
RRBs	9.19	1.51	6.23	10.69	50881.85	3.88
Private Bank	0.79	1.09	1.06	1.88	8043.39	1.52
Rural Cooperative Bank	0.19	0.00	0.10	0.19	0.01	0.00
Total	44.34	12.43	31.66	56.77	273658.41	39.15

Source: Website of PMJDY: www.pmjdy.gov.in

According to Table-2, the total number of PMJDY accounts as of 15 Oct 2025 was 56.77 crore, with a deposit amount of Rs.273658.41 crore. More than 44.34 crore (78.10%) of these accounts were opened at rural/semi urban bank branches, whereas 12.43 crore (21.89%) were opened at urban bank branches. The table also shows that Public Sector banks opened more than 44.01 crore (77.52%) accounts, while Rural Regional Banks (RRBs) opened more than 10.69 crore (18.83%) accounts, Private banks opened only 1.88 crore accounts and Rural Cooperative Bank 0.19 crore (0.33%). Beneficiaries received around 39.15 crore Rupay debit cards.

Result and Discussion

Major Achievement of PMJDY towards Financial Inclusion

The National Mission for Financial Inclusion's Pradhan Mantri Jan-DhanYojana (PMJDY) was launched on August 28th, 2014, for a four-year (in two parts) duration. It advocates for universal banking services, with each family having at least one basic banking account, as well as financial literacy, credit, insurance, and pensions. On June 20, 2015, the PMJDY project set a Guinness World Record for opening the most bank accounts in the shortest amount of time. In September 2018, the government revived PMJDY as an open-ended plan with additional benefits to encourage people to open bank accounts, bolstered by the scheme's success. The government wants to give 'every household' access to the official banking system.

56.77 crore Jan Dhan accounts opened (as of 15th Oct 2025).

55.7% (31.66 crore) Jan-Dhan account holders are women

78.10% (44.34 crore) of Jan Dhan accounts are in rural and semi-urban areas

During the first year of the scheme, 17.90 crore PMJDY accounts were opened.

The number of PMJDY accounts has grown more than three-fold from 14.72 crore in March 2015 to 50.09 crore in August 2023.

Total deposit balances under PMJDY Accounts stand at Rs. 273658.41 crore (as of 15th Oct 2025)

56% Jan Dhan accounts belong to women, highlighting the scheme's role in promoting gender equality in financial access. Women, especially in the unorganised sector, have benefited from access to social security and credit schemes like PMJJBY, PMSBY, and APY.

Total RuPay cards issued to PMJDY account holders: 39.15 crore (as of 15/10/2024). Number of RuPay cards in January 2024 is up by over 2.5 times compared to the number of RuPay cards in March 2015.

Jan Dhan Darshak App: A mobile application was launched to provide a citizen-centric platform for locating banking touch points such as bank branches, ATMs, Bank Mitras, Post Offices, etc. In the country. Over 13 lakh banking touchpoints have been mapped on the JDD App.

Under PM Garib KalyanYojana, an amount of Rs. 500 per month for three months (April 2020 to June 2020), was credited to the accounts of women account holders under PMJDY. A total of Rs. 30,945 crores have been credited in accounts of women PMJDY account holders during the COVID lockdown.

Conclusion

The Financial Inclusion ecosystem is growing, and the nine-year course of interventions led by PMJDY has really produced transformative and directed change that has made banking and financial services available to the poorest of the poor. PMJDY is that where people-centred economic initiatives first emerged. It was necessary to open the accounts of the poor in order to provide the advantages of a number of government schemes and welfare programmes to them and this aim was achieved under PMJDY system. A multitude of government schemes, such as COVID-19 financial aid, direct benefit payments, PM KISAN, increased wages under MGNREGA, and life and health insurance coverage, these are directly deposited into their bank accounts are currently providing financial aid to over 38 crore PMJDY account holders. Between March 2014 and March 2016, PMJDY accounts were opened with enormous energy and it gained the rate of one account per

second. Ex-gratia payments were made to over 20 crore women's PMJDY accounts within 10 days of the lockdown in 2020 during COVID-19.

The Jan Dhan account made the poor free from the control of predatory money lenders and gave them a way to transfer money to their family in the villages and enter their savings into the formal financial system. The PMJDY account has also improved India's financial infrastructure, enabling the vast majority of its adult population to access financial services. During the COVID19 pandemic, Direct Benefit Transfers (DBTs) have empowered and given financial security to the most vulnerable members of society. The fact that DBTs made possible by PM Jan Dhan accounts has stopped systematic leakage and make sure that every rupee reaches its designated beneficiary."A rupee provided by the centre is only worth 15 paisa by the time it reaches the beneficiary," as former prime minister Rajiv Gandhi famously said. Instead, it now guarantees that all government aid beneficiaries receive 100% of their funds through direct benefit transfers into the 37 crore accounts that were opened through PMJDY. Thus, "Mera Khata Bhagya Vidhata," the slogan of the PMJDY, is deemed fully accomplished.

Suggestions for the future Study

Suggestions For Effective Implementation of Scheme

Make every effort to guarantee that PMJDY account holders are covered by micro insurance schemes. PMJDY account holders who are eligible will be sought to be insured under PMJJBY and PMSBY. Banks have already been informed of the situation.

Promotion of digital payments, including the use of RuPay debit cards, among PMJDY account holders through the establishment of acceptance infrastructure throughout India
Improving PMJDY account holder's access to microcredit and micro investment opportunities such as flexi-recurring deposits, etc.

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